

ENHANCING STUDENT MOTIVATION THROUGH AN INTERCULTURAL APPROACH TO READING MATERIALS

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Modern educators agree that the quality of the performance of an activity and its result depend, first of all, on the motivation and needs of the individual and they have already proved that it is motivation that causes purposeful activity that determines the choice of means and methods, their ordering to achieve goals.

The word motivation was first used by A.Schopenhauer in his article “The Four Principles of Sufficient Cause” (1900-1910). Then this term became firmly established in psychological use to explain the causes of human and animal behavior [4:65]. In addition, we can find several definitions of the concept of motivation in the internet, pedagogical and psychological literature.

According to wiki materials, motivation is the reason for which humans and other animals initiate, continue, or terminate a behavior at a given time [7].

Summarizing the above points, we can say that the concept of motivation is a system of motives (needs, intentions, goals, interests, aspirations) that determine behavior. So, motivation is a concept consisting of different motives. There are given different definitions to motives, but there is no single definition of motive accepted by all scientists.

V.G.Leontiev cited by E.P.Ilin considers the motive as a systemic formation of the personality, as a systemic way of organizing human activity. [4:116]. A motive is a periodically recurring interest in a target state based on a natural impulse [5:15]. Therefore, the motive is the interest and activity based on the natural impulse of the systematic formation of the person.

In general, motivation is a tool that helps you understand how to develop instruction in the classroom. Many teachers believe that they can create a learning environment in the classroom by following the language materials and trying to regulate their stubborn students. However, teachers ignore the fact that they cannot motivate their students if they do not understand the identity of their students and work on the small details that build their social and psychological structure.

In our opinion, the best way to achieve this goal is to teach English through the development of reading skills.

Reading is widely recognized as one of the most significant second-language abilities because it allows language learners to acquire a wide range of lexical items, grammatical structures, and additional schematic knowledge through reading. Despite the fact that being able to read fluently in a foreign language is usually regarded as one of the most significant abilities a foreign language student can possess, teaching reading poses a number of pedagogical and logistical obstacles.

A text chosen for studying is anticipated to be authentic-made or authentic-like, not too hard for the learners, suitable for the teaching intention and usable in the sequence of activities, lending itself as a useful resource of information and ideas.

There are so many challenges in teaching reading in EFL classroom of Karakalpakstan. Teaching reading a passage is considered the easiest of all the activities that a teacher does in a foreign language classroom. Generally, teachers come to class without any preparation and

they give a long lecture on the content. They don't care if the text is appropriate for the learner or not. Furthermore, they attach little importance to language teaching, language learners and their interests.

The peculiarity of linguistics in the age of globalization is to pay attention to the intercultural aspects of language acquisition. This leads teachers and scholars to reconsider existing programmatic approaches to learning it, as well as to develop more effective methods of learning another culture. During this period, new theories and concepts of foreign language learning from the cultural point of view are being observed in local pedagogy, and it requires changing and modernizing the theoretical foundations of foreign language teaching.

Professor J.Jalolov "... a language, including a non-native one, is acquired at the same time as a reflection of the culture of the country or native speaker. Therefore, over the past two decades, issues of teaching language along with culture have been intensively developed, for example, teaching English language and culture." [3:90]. As can be seen from this idea, we can notice that nowadays in the English language methodology, great attention is being paid to teaching the language through culture.

Before discussing the cross-cultural aspects of English language teaching, let's first consider what definitions and ideas are given about culture.

According to the information of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization UNESCO: Culture is the set of distinctive spiritual, material, intellectual and emotional features of society or a social group, noting that this includes lifestyles, value systems, traditions, and beliefs in addition to creative works [1].

In the Cambridge Online Dictionary, culture is defined as the way of life, especially the general customs and beliefs, of a particular group of people at a particular time [8]. So, based on the given definitions, culture is the traditions, actions, history, creativity, manners, moral status and way of life of the members of a certain society.

A foreign language is learned in a completely different cultural context, that is, in the conditions of the students' own culture, which ensures dialogue between cultures in the educational process, contributes to a better understanding of similarities and differences between them. "Therefore, any study of culture and, especially, on the material of fictional literature, occurs on the basis of a comparison of one's own and someone else's culture. It is this aspect that is of considerable interest for the methodology of teaching a foreign language, as it allows you to build a scheme for studying culture in a comparative aspect." [6:4].

We believe that, first of all, in order to form the intercultural competence of schoolchildren in a foreign language classroom, we should use reading materials as a basis. Today's English reading materials have a wide range of knowledge and a large amount of information, which involves various cultural knowledge of the source language countries, including historical geography, local customs, traditional customs, behavioral norms, social etiquette, values and so on [2:150-151]. Therefore, most of the information in school textbooks is presented in the form of reading skills, and students can learn a variety of interesting cultural information from them. This, in turn, leads to an increase in the student's motivation of learning English.

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